

ON THE BROCARD–RAMANUJAN EQUATION WITH 7-FREE
INTEGERS AND PRIME POWERS

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Abstract

This paper proves that for any integer $k \geq 2$, the Brocard–Ramanujan Diophantine equation $n! + 1 = x^2$ has only finitely many integer solutions (n, x) , assuming $x \pm 1$ is a k -free integer or has less than k prime divisors. Specifically, we identify all integer solutions when $x \pm 1$ is a 7-free integer or a prime power. We then extend this result and make a remark on the resolution of the Brocard–Ramanujan problem.

1. Introduction

The Brocard–Ramanujan problem (see [4] and [18]) concerns the Diophantine equation

$$n! + 1 = x^2. \tag{1}$$

Only three solutions are known: $(4, 5)$, $(5, 11)$, and $(7, 71)$. Extensive computations up to 10^9 (see [2]) have yielded no additional solutions, suggesting these three pairs may be exhaustive. Despite numerous attempts and varied approaches, this problem remains unsolved. A review of the existing literature reveals that three major approaches have been used to address Equation (1). The first is the variant-based approach, which consists of studying modified versions of Equation (1) (see, for example, [1], [5], [6], [7], [10], [12], [19], [20]). The second consists of solving Equation (1) under the abc conjecture or its variants (see [5], [11], [15]). The third is the subset-based approach, which focuses on exploring solutions within specific subsets of \mathbb{N} . More specifically, it involves solving, for a given integer sequence (u_m) , the equation $n! + 1 = u_m^2$, where n and m are the unknowns. Regarding this latter approach, recent studies have explored several variants of the Brocard–Ramanujan Diophantine equation. D. Marques [14] proved that the Fibonacci version, $n! + 1 = F_m^2$, has no solution except for $(n, m) = (4, 5)$. J. J. Bravo

et al. [3] demonstrated that the Tripell version admits no solution except $(4, 3)$. M. Ismail et al. [9] showed that the Narayana version has no solution. P. T. Young [21] obtained similar results for the Tribonacci and Tetranacci versions. Finally, the author [13] observed that Sylvester’s version has no positive integer solutions. Additional versions involving recurrence sequences can be found in references [16] and [17].

This paper explores new subsets of \mathbb{N} with a finite number of solutions to Equation (1). We begin by establishing the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *The following statements hold.*

(i) *For any given integer $k \geq 2$, there are only finitely many integer solutions (n, x) to the Brocard–Ramanujan equation $n! + 1 = x^2$, where $x \pm 1$ is a k -free number. Specifically, this equation has at most the three pairs $(4, 5)$, $(5, 11)$, and $(7, 71)$ as solutions where $x \pm 1$ is a 7-free integer.*

(ii) *For any given integer $l \geq 2$, there are only finitely many integer solutions (n, x) to the Brocard–Ramanujan equation $n! + 1 = x^2$, where $x \pm 1$ has less than l prime divisors. Specifically, this equation has at most the pair $(4, 5)$ as a solution where $x \pm 1$ is a prime power.*

In Section 4, we provide a generalization of Theorem 1 and make a remark on the resolution of the Brocard–Ramanujan problem.

2. Preliminary Results

We begin by recalling classical number theoretic results. Let $\pi(n)$ denote the number of primes less than or equal to n . The Prime Number Theorem states that $\pi(n) \sim \frac{n}{\ln(n)}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Furthermore, Chebyshev’s theorem refinement yields

$$\frac{n}{\ln(n)} \leq \pi(n) \leq \frac{3}{2} \frac{n}{\ln(n)}, \text{ for all } n \geq 2.$$

Stirling’s formula states that $n!$ asymptotically behaves like $n^n \exp(-n)\sqrt{2\pi n}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Moreover, for all $n \geq 1$, we have

$$\left(\frac{n}{e}\right)^n \leq n! \leq n^n.$$

For a prime p , let $\nu_p(n)$ denote the largest power of p dividing n . Legendre’s formula states:

$$\nu_p(n!) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \left\lfloor \frac{n}{p^i} \right\rfloor,$$

where $[x]$ is the integer part of x . This yields

$$\nu_p(n!) \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{n}{p^i} = \frac{n}{p-1}.$$

Thus, if p^α divides $n!$, then $p \leq n$ and $\alpha \leq \frac{n}{p-1}$. All these classic results can be found in the reference [8].

For all positive integer x , we let $\omega(x)$ denote the number of distinct primes in the prime factorization of x and we let $K(x)$ denote the maximum exponent in the prime factorization of x . That is, if the prime factorization of x is

$$x = \prod_{i \in I} p_i^{\alpha_i},$$

then we have $\omega(x) = |I|$ and $K(x) = \max_{i \in I} \alpha_i$.

Lemma 1. *Let n and x be positive integers. If x divides $n!$, then*

$$x \leq \exp\left(\frac{3nK(x)}{2}\right).$$

Proof. Let $x = \prod_{i \in I} p_i^{\alpha_i}$ be the prime factorization of x . By definition of $K(x)$, we have $\alpha_i \leq K(x)$ for all $i \in I$. Thus, $x \leq \prod_{i \in I} p_i^{K(x)}$. Since x divides $n!$, every prime factor p_i satisfies $p_i \leq n$. Moreover, the number of distinct prime factors, $|I|$, is bounded by $\pi(n)$. Therefore we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &\leq n^{K(x)|I|} \\ &\leq n^{K(x)\pi(n)} \\ &\leq n^{\frac{3nK(x)}{2} \frac{1}{\ln(n)}} \\ &= \exp\left(\frac{3nK(x)}{2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 2. *Let n, x be positive integers. If x divides $n!$, then*

$$x \leq n^{\frac{n}{a}} \left(a\omega(x) + 1 \right)^{n\omega(x)},$$

for any arbitrary positive integer a .

Proof. Let $x = \prod_{i \in I} p_i^{\alpha_i}$ be the prime factorization of x and assume that x divides $n!$. Note that $|I| = \omega(x)$, $p_i \leq n$ for all $i \in I$, and $\alpha_i \leq \frac{n}{p_i-1}$ for all $i \in I$. For a positive integer a , define:

$$J = \left\{ i \in I \mid p_i \leq a\omega(x) + 1 \right\}.$$

So we have

$$\sum_{i \in J} \alpha_i \leq \sum_{i \in I} \frac{n}{p_i - 1} \leq \sum_{i \in I} n = n\omega(x)$$

and

$$\sum_{i \in I \setminus J} \alpha_i \leq \sum_{i \in I \setminus J} \frac{n}{p_i - 1} \leq \sum_{i \in I \setminus J} \frac{n}{a\omega(x)} \leq \sum_{i \in I} \frac{n}{a\omega(x)} = \frac{n}{a}.$$

Therefore,

$$x = \prod_{i \in I} p_i^{\alpha_i} = \prod_{i \in J} p_i^{\alpha_i} \prod_{i \in I \setminus J} p_i^{\alpha_i} \leq (a\omega(x) + 1)^{\sum_{i \in J} \alpha_i} n^{\sum_{i \in I \setminus J} \alpha_i} \leq (a\omega(x) + 1)^{n\omega(x)} n^{\frac{n}{a}}.$$

□

3. Proof of Theorem 1

We now apply the preceding lemmas to prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. (i) Let k be a positive integer. We simultaneously consider the cases where $x - 1$ and $x + 1$ are k -free, relying on the inequality

$$(x - \varepsilon)(x + \varepsilon) \leq 2(x - \varepsilon)^2, \text{ for } \varepsilon = \pm 1 \text{ and } x \geq 3.$$

Let $\varepsilon = \pm 1$. Suppose (n, x) satisfies Equation (1), where $x \geq 3$ and $x - \varepsilon$ is a k -free integer, i.e., $K(x - \varepsilon) < k$. Since $x - \varepsilon$ divides $n! = (x - \varepsilon)(x + \varepsilon)$, Lemma 1 yields

$$x - \varepsilon \leq \exp\left(\frac{3nK(x - \varepsilon)}{2}\right) \leq \exp\left(\frac{3nk}{2}\right),$$

and hence

$$n! = (x - \varepsilon)(x + \varepsilon) \leq 2(x - \varepsilon)^2 \leq 2 \exp(3nk).$$

Using Stirling's inequality,

$$\left(\frac{n}{e}\right)^n \leq n!,$$

implying

$$\left(\frac{n}{e}\right)^n \leq 2 \exp(3nk),$$

and hence

$$n \leq 2 \exp(3k + 1). \tag{2}$$

Therefore, there are only finitely many solutions.

For solutions (n, x) of Equation (1), with $x \pm 1$ a 7-free integer, i.e., $k \leq 6$, Inequality (2) yields $n \leq 2 \exp(19) < 10^9$. So, according to Berndt and Galway's computations [2], the possible solutions are $(4, 5)$, $(5, 11)$, and $(7, 71)$.

(ii) Let l be a positive integer and $\varepsilon = \pm 1$. Suppose (n, x) satisfies Equation (1), where $x \geq 3$ and $x - \varepsilon$ has fewer than l prime divisors, i.e., $\omega(x - \varepsilon) < l$. Applying Lemma 2, with $a = 4$, we obtain

$$x - \varepsilon \leq n^{\frac{n}{4}} \left(4\omega(x - \varepsilon) + 1\right)^{n\omega(x - \varepsilon)} \leq n^{\frac{n}{4}} (4l + 1)^{nl},$$

and hence

$$n! = (x - \varepsilon)(x + \varepsilon) \leq 2(x - \varepsilon)^2 \leq 2n^{\frac{n}{2}} (4l + 1)^{2nl}.$$

Now, applying Stirling's inequality yields

$$\left(\frac{n}{e}\right)^n \leq n! \leq 2n^{\frac{n}{2}} (4l + 1)^{2nl},$$

which simplifies to

$$\left(\frac{n}{e}\right) \leq 2\sqrt{n}(4l + 1)^{2l}.$$

Thus,

$$n \leq 4e^2(4l + 1)^{4l}, \tag{3}$$

establishing that the number of solutions is finite.

For solutions (n, x) of Equation (1), with $x \pm 1$ a prime power, Inequality (3) yields $n \leq 4e^{29^8} < 10^9$. Then the possible solution is $(4, 5)$, according to Berndt and Galway's computations [2]. \square

Remark. Consider the sequence (u_m) of Fermat (respectively, Mersenne) numbers. Since $u_m - 1$ (respectively, $u_m + 1$) is a prime power, the Diophantine equation $n! + 1 = u_n^2$ admits a unique solution $(n, m) = (4, 1)$ (respectively, no solutions).

4. Generalization

For any pair (k, l) of positive integers ≥ 2 , let us define

$$\mathcal{F}_k = \{x \in \mathbb{N} \mid K(x) < k\} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{P}_l = \{x \in \mathbb{N} \mid \omega(x) < l\}.$$

Their product set, $\mathcal{F}_k \mathcal{P}_l$, consists of integers yz with $y \in \mathcal{F}_k$ and $z \in \mathcal{P}_l$. Note that $\mathcal{F}_k \mathcal{P}_l$ is larger than the union $\mathcal{F}_k \cup \mathcal{P}_l$.

Theorem 1 established that for any pair (k, l) of positive integers ≥ 2 , the Brocard–Ramanujan equation has finitely many solutions (n, x) , where x belongs to the set

$$S = \{x_1 \pm 1 \mid x_1 \in \mathcal{F}_k \cup \mathcal{P}_l\}.$$

This set can be considered a large one in the sense that its natural density is non-zero. Indeed, it is well known (see, for example, [8]) that the natural density of \mathcal{F}_k alone equals $\frac{1}{\zeta(k)}$, where ζ is the Riemann function. To further enlarge S , we introduce multivariate polynomials where variables take values from $\mathcal{F}_k \mathcal{P}_l$, replacing $\mathcal{F}_k \cup \mathcal{P}_l$.

Theorem 2. *Let k, l , and m be positive integers, with $k, l \geq 2$. Let P be a polynomial in m variables with integers coefficients and define*

$$S = \{x_1 \dots x_m P(x_1, \dots, x_m) \pm 1 \mid x_1, \dots, x_m \in \mathcal{F}_k \mathcal{P}_l\}.$$

Then the Brocard–Ramanujan Diophantine equation $n! + 1 = x^2$ has only finitely many integer solutions where x belongs to S .

Proof. Let us write the polynomial

$$Q = X_1 \dots X_m P(X_1, \dots, X_m) (X_1 \dots X_m P(X_1, \dots, X_m) \pm 2)$$

in the form:

$$Q = \sum_{(i_1, \dots, i_m) \in L} a_{i_1, \dots, i_m} X_1^{i_1} \dots X_m^{i_m},$$

with L a finite subset of \mathbb{N}^m and $a_{i_1, \dots, i_m} \in \mathbb{Z}$, for all $(i_1, \dots, i_m) \in L$. The total degree of Q is given by

$$d = \max_{(i_1, \dots, i_m) \in L} i_1 + i_2 + \dots + i_m.$$

Define

$$M = \sum_{(i_1, \dots, i_m) \in L} |a_{i_1, \dots, i_m}|$$

and note that for all positive integers x_1, \dots, x_m , the following inequality holds:

$$Q(x_1, \dots, x_m) \leq M \left(\max_{1 \leq i \leq m} x_i \right)^d. \tag{4}$$

Now assume (n, x) is a positive integer pair satisfying $n! + 1 = x^2$, with $x \in S$, i.e., $x = x_1 \dots x_m P(x_1, \dots, x_m) \pm 1$ for some $x_1, \dots, x_m \in \mathcal{F}_k \mathcal{P}_l$. We will demonstrate that n is bounded.

From $n! + 1 = x^2$, we obtain

$$n! = Q(x_1, \dots, x_m).$$

Using (4), we deduce

$$n! \leq M \left(\max_{1 \leq i \leq m} x_i \right)^d. \tag{5}$$

On the other hand, let i_0 be an index such that $x_{i_0} = \max_{1 \leq i \leq m} x_i$ and let $y \in \mathcal{F}_k$ and $z \in \mathcal{P}_l$ such that $x_{i_0} = yz$. By Lemma 1, since y divides $n!$, we have

$$y \leq \exp \left(\frac{3kn}{2} \right).$$

Applying Lemma 2, with $a = 2d$, yields

$$z \leq n^{\frac{n}{2d}} (2dl + 1)^{ln}.$$

Combining these inequalities with (5), we obtain

$$n! \leq M \left(\exp \left(\frac{3kn}{2} \right) n^{\frac{n}{2d}} (2dl + 1)^{ln} \right)^d.$$

Now applying Stirling's inequality yields

$$\left(\frac{n}{e} \right)^n \leq n! \leq M \left(\exp \left(\frac{3kn}{2} \right) n^{\frac{n}{2d}} (2dl + 1)^{ln} \right)^d.$$

Taking into account that M is a positive integer and $M^{\frac{1}{n}} \leq M$, this inequality simplifies to

$$\frac{n}{e} \leq M \exp \left(\frac{3kd}{2} \right) \sqrt{n} (2dl + 1)^{dl}.$$

Thus

$$n \leq M^2 \exp (3kd + 2) (2dl + 1)^{2dl},$$

establishing that the number of solutions is finite. □

Remark on the Resolution of the Brocard–Ramanujan Problem. Let us now observe the set \mathcal{S} from Theorem 2, where the equation $n! + 1 = x^2$ admits only finitely many solutions. This set is parameterized by a multivariate polynomial, with variables running through the large set $\mathcal{F}_k \mathcal{P}_l$. So the potential size of \mathcal{S} raises an intriguing question: For a suitable multivariate polynomial P , does \mathcal{S} encompass all odd positive integers, except perhaps a few, for sufficiently large k and l ? Affirming this would resolve the Brocard–Ramanujan problem, according to Theorem 2.

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